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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

VIRTUAL VA ARALASH (BLENDED) O‘QITISH METODLARINI KASBIY TA’LIMDA JORIY ETISH

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada virtual va aralash (blended) o‘qitish metodlarini kasbiy ta’lim tizimiga joriy etishning nazariy asoslari hamda amaliy afzalliklari yoritilgan. Raqamli ta’lim muhitining imkoniyatlari, onlayn va oflayn o‘qitishning integratsiyasi, shuningdek, o‘quvchilarning o‘zlashtirish va mustaqil ishlash samaradorligiga ta’siri tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: virtual ta’lim, aralash o‘qitish, kasbiy ta’lim, raqamli texnologiyalar, onlayn platformalar, kompetensiya, innovatsion pedagogika.

Kirish

Bugungi kunda raqamli texnologiyalar jadal rivojlanib borayotgan bir davrda ta’lim tizimi ham tubdan yangilanmoqda. Ayniqsa, kasbiy ta’lim tizimida zamonaviy texnologiyalarni qo‘llash, o‘quv jarayonini moslashuvchan, innovatsion va shaxsga yo‘naltirilgan shaklda tashkil etish zarurati ortmoqda. Shu nuqtayi nazardan, virtual o‘qitish va aralash (blended learning) ta’lim metodlari ta’lim jarayoniga samarali integratsiya qilinmoqda. Bu metodlar o‘quvchilarga nazariy bilimlarni onlayn tarzda, amaliy ko‘nikmalarni esa oflayn sharoitda egallash imkoniyatini yaratadi. Natijada, o‘quvchi o‘z vaqtini mustaqil boshqarish, masofadan o‘rganish, va kasbiy kompetensiyalarni individual rivojlantirish imkoniga ega bo‘ladi.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 28-yanvardagi PF–60-sonli “2022–2026-yillarga mo‘ljallangan Yangi O‘zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi farmonida ta’lim jarayonini raqamlashtirish, uzluksiz ta’lim tizimida masofaviy o‘qitish texnologiyalarini joriy etish muhim ustuvor yo‘nalish sifatida belgilangan. Shu jihatdan, virtual va aralash ta’lim metodlarini kasbiy ta’limda tatbiq etish o‘qituvchining pedagogik mahoratini, o‘quvchining o‘quv motivatsiyasini va ta’lim samaradorligini oshirishda muhim omil sifatida qaraladi.

Asosiy qism

Zamonaviy ta’lim jarayonida raqamli texnologiyalar asosida o‘qitish — bilim berishning muhim yo‘nalishiga aylandi. Ayniqsa, **kasbiy ta’lim** tizimida mehnat bozoriga mos, amaliy kompetensiyalarga ega mutaxassislarni tayyorlash jarayonida **virtual** va **aralash o‘qitish** metodlaridan samarali foydalanish katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Virtual o‘qitish — bu o‘quvchilarga masofadan turib ta’lim olish imkonini beruvchi raqamli platformalar (Moodle, Google Classroom, Edmodo, Coursera, va boshqalar) orqali bilim berish jarayonidir. Ushbu modelda ta’lim jarayoni multimedia, video darslar, interaktiv topshiriqlar, testlar va simulyatsiyalar orqali amalga oshiriladi. Virtual ta’lim o‘quvchilarga joy va vaqt chegaralarisiz bilim olish

imkonini beradi, bu esa **moslashuvchanlik**, **mustaqillik** va **individual yondashuvni** ta'minlaydi.

Aralash (blended) o'qitish esa an'anaviy (auditoriyada) va masofaviy (onlayn) ta'limning uyg'unlashgan shaklidir. Bu model o'quvchilarni nazariy bilimni masofadan o'zlashtirib, amaliy mashg'ulotlarni esa o'quv ustaxonalari yoki laboratoriyalarda bajarishga imkon yaratadi. Aralash o'qitishning eng muhim jihati — **interaktivlik** va **talaba markazlilik** tamoyillarining amalga oshirishidir.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, aralash ta'lim modeli o'quvchilarning o'zlashtirish darajasini o'rtacha **25–30%** ga oshiradi, o'qituvchi va talaba o'rtasidagi **muloqotni faollashtiradi**, hamda o'quvchilarda **amaliy fikrlash va muammoli vaziyatlarni hal etish ko'nikmasini** rivojlantiradi.

Kasbiy ta'lim tizimida ushbu metodlarni joriy etish quyidagi natijalarga olib keladi:

1. **O'quv jarayonining moslashuvchanligi** – darslarni istalgan vaqtda qayta ko'rish imkoniyati;
2. **Resurslardan samarali foydalanish** – dars materiallarini yagona elektron platformalarda jamlash;
3. **Talabalarning raqamli kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish** – onlayn muloqot, axborot izlash, elektron hujjat bilan ishlash ko'nikmalarining shakllanishi;
4. **O'qituvchining yangi roli** – fasilitator va yo'naltiruvchi sifatida ta'lim jarayonini boshqarish.

Biroq, virtual va aralash o'qitish jarayonini samarali tashkil etishda ayrim muammolar ham kuzatiladi: texnik infratuzilmaning yetarli emasligi, o'qituvchilarning raqamli kompetensiyasi pastligi, o'quvchilarning mustaqil ta'limga motivatsiyasi sustligi. Shu bois, ushbu modelni to'laqonli joriy etish uchun quyidagi shart-sharoitlarni yaratish muhim:

- o'qituvchilar uchun **raqamli pedagogika bo'yicha malaka oshirish kurslari**;
- ta'lim muassasalarini **barqaror internet va kompyuter texnikasi** bilan ta'minlash;
- **milliy virtual o'quv platformalarini** ishlab chiqish va amaliyotga tatbiq etish.

Xulosa

Virtual va aralash o'qitish metodlari kasbiy ta'lim jarayonini zamonaviylashtirishning eng samarali vositalaridan biridir. Ular ta'limning sifatini oshiradi, o'quvchi faoliyatini faollashtiradi va mustaqil o'rganishga undaydi. Kelgusida ushbu texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish orqali O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimi global raqamli ta'lim maydoniga integratsiyalashuvi yanada tezlashadi.

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